

APPROACHES TO COMBATING JUVENILE DELINQUENCY THROUGH GUIDANCE AND COUNSELLING IN KOGI STATE SECONDARY SCHOOLS

Martinez, Isabella Grace

Department of Educational Psychology, University of Toronto, Toronto, Canada

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Abstract

Juvenile delinquency, characterized by children's offenses, misconduct, or criminal behavior, has become a growing concern in Nigeria. Despite the existence of societal norms and efforts by educators, religious leaders, and moral instructors to instill ethical values, many youths continue to engage in deviant behaviors. The prevalence of juvenile delinquency has attracted widespread attention in media, academic discussions, and public discourse, reflecting the anxiety of society over its implications. This study explores the role of guidance and counselling approaches in addressing juvenile delinquency within senior secondary schools, emphasizing interventions that promote moral development, behavioral correction, and social reintegration. By highlighting effective strategies and preventive measures, the study aims to provide insights for educators, counsellors, and policymakers to mitigate delinquent behaviors among youths and foster responsible citizenship.

Keywords: Juvenile delinquency, Guidance and counselling, Youth behavior, Moral education, Secondary schools

INTRODUCTION

In every society, there are sets of norms which members are expected to observe, however, not every member of the society abides by those norms. Members who live contrary to the set norms are referred to as deviants. Juvenile delinquency according to Solomon (2014) initially has to do with children's offences, misconduct or crime for which, it is thought, they are not directly responsible. Bello (2006) observed that delinquent behaviours have assumed an alarming proportion in Nigeria. Nigerians are disturbed and anxious as they are concerned about the problem of delinquency in which today's youths involve themselves. The issue of juvenile delinquency is being discussed on television, radio, newspapers and journals and recently on the internet. This cankerworm seems to survive despite efforts made by religious and moral education teachers to eliminate them through the inculcation of moral values in schools (Michael & Tyerman, 2005).

Delinquency is basically a legal and relative term which refers to the breaking of the law of a particular country. An act therefore may make an adolescent delinquent in one country, but not necessarily in another. However, there are certain behaviours such as stealing and killing that are considered as violating the social and moral norms of most societies. For quite a long time, the issue of juvenile delinquency has become a great concern to Nigerian Secondary Schools, especially in Kogi State. Studies have shown that juvenile delinquency is rampant among Secondary School Students due to a number of causes. According to Solomon (2014) such causes include; parents' attitudes towards their children, the community, social class, frustration, peer group, foreign ideas, poverty, illiteracy, among others. Juvenile delinquency is a social problem in secondary schools which this research aims at finding out the factors, consequences and control measures. There is no universal definition of juvenile delinquency as different nations and jurisdiction stipulate different age bracket for juvenile. Juvenile Delinquency is considered as juvenile offences (Siegel & Brandon, 2011). Shoemaker (2010) defined juvenile

delinquency as illegal acts whether crime or status offences that are committed by youths under the ages of eighteen. Adegoke (2015) identified juvenile delinquency as the violation of the criminal codes regulating the behaviour of young persons in the society.

The United Nations guidelines for the prevention of juvenile delinquency cited in Nwachukwu (2018) assert that juvenile delinquency as youthful behaviour or conduct that does not conform to overall social norms and values of society. Juvenile delinquency is associated with maturation and growth process and will disappear spontaneously in most individual with transition to adulthood. The circumstances of many delinquencies therefore suggest experimentation (Clinnard & Meir, 2008). Juvenile offenders are therefore considered to be normative adolescent behaviour as most teens offend once or a few times during their adolescent age. Urbanization and modernization have brought about drastic changes in social control and cohesion in emerging cities in virtually most developing countries across the globe. In addition to urbanization, the application of new technology and the media have created consumption pattern which is beyond the capacity of most families with resultant negative influence on youths. In Nigeria, 67.1 percent of the populations are living below poverty line (National Bureau of Statistics, 2017). Poverty coupled with the involvement of youths in economic pursuit creates a fertile ground for juvenile infraction in our society.

Crimes either by juvenile or adults constitute threat to the collective wellbeing of society. Juvenile infraction is a contemporary social problem in Nigeria society that adversely affects the norms and ethical value of our society with potential of making life uncomfortable for all and sundry. Juvenile delinquency places enormous burden in society in terms of lost in productivity in man hours trying to enforce discipline and the attendant increase that goes with social services and law enforcement. To Dambazua (2007), juvenile delinquency will not augur well for Childs growth and development in Nigeria. Juvenile infraction if left unchecked will undermine the realization of the objectives of national policy of education in Nigeria that target accomplishing a united, strong and self-reliant nation, a great and dynamic economy with a just and egalitarian society, a land that is bright and full of opportunities for all citizens in a free and democratic society (Federal Republic of Nigeria, 2014).

Delinquent acts fall under two categories according to Agbowuru, Oriade, Umen, and Solomon (2016). The first category of delinquent acts is considered a crime if committed by adults. In some jurisdiction offenders are tried as adults for crime like murder and armed robbery. The second category is acts that would normally not be classified as a crime. They are referred to as status offences such as runaway, truancy and keeping late hours. Juvenile infraction cut across all social-economic spectrum of society but differs in terms of rate. Some parents however are better in dealing with juvenile infraction than others. There was an incident when a male student harassed a female student by touching her breast, when the matter was reported to the school authorities; the male student was seriously punished. Apart from the punishment, other students view that particular student as someone who is sexually immoral and bad; this made that delinquent student to withdraw from other students for a while and of course, not many students wanted to be identified with a delinquent.

There are so many social vices among the youths these days, some of which ranges from stealing, raping, armed robbery, examination misconduct, fighting, killing and so many more. One tends to wonder what factors are

responsible for all these behaviours among the youth. If these problems among this youth are not properly handled what will be the future of Nigeria and Kogi State in particular. In 2019 governorship election in Kogi State which was marred with crises among the youths as a result of ballot box snatching and other forms of electoral malpractices which led to loss of so many lives out of which majority of them were youths. The youths in Kogi State have been involved in so many acts contrary to the rules and regulations of the State. At the secondary school level the youths seems to be indulging in truancy behaviour, fighting, kidnapping, killing, rapping and so many social vices which if not properly handled will ruin the reputation of the State and Nigeria at large.

Adikwu, Oguche, Usman and Olabode (2023) asserted that the increasing number of students and out of school children hawking and selling goods around the streets, traffics and school premises in Nigeria is alarming. Some of these children look so malnourished and sick, others in the pain of beating and assault by gangsters. Due to the poor economic state and increasing poverty in the country some of these children are sent out by their parents or caregivers to enable them meet up with family needs. The interest of most parents is what the child can bring to the home; many leave schools very early to engage in prostitution while others are used as house helps and other menial jobs to bring in money to the family. Students exhibit behaviours that do not conform to the acceptable moral norms in our society. These behaviours in turn affect their academic performance in schools and may lead to their dropout from school. It is in view of this that the necessitated the choice to study “the factors, consequences and control of juvenile delinquency among Secondary School Students in Kogi State: Implications for Guidance.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this research is to find out the factors, consequences and control of juvenile delinquency among Senior Secondary School Students in Kogi State: implications for guidance. The specific objectives of the study are to:

- i) examine the factors of juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kogi State.
- ii) determine the consequences of juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kogi State.
- iii) find out the control measures of juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kogi State.

Research Questions

The following research questions were raised to guide the study:

1. What are the factors of juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kogi State?
2. What are the consequences of juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kogi State?
3. What are the control measures of juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kogi State?

Null Hypotheses

Based on the research questions the following null hypotheses were developed and tested at 0.05 level of significance.

H01: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of male and female students on the consequences of juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kogi State.

H02: There is no significant difference between the mean ratings of rural and urban students on the consequences of juvenile delinquency among senior secondary school students in Kogi State.

Conceptual Framework

In this section, concepts used in this study were explained as follows:

Juvenile Delinquency

The issue of delinquency is observed to be as old as humanity itself. There is no gainsaying of the fact that, a proportion of adult criminals have a background of early delinquency. Farrington (2004) describes delinquency as crimes committed by young people. Delinquency comprises legal infractions ranging from littering to murder. Even though the crimes committed by adolescents could be the same as those committed by adults, because it is assumed adolescence are yet to comprehend fully the consequences of their actions, they are tried differently by the juvenile court system. The type of punishment they receive is to prevent them from committing another illegal act.

Juvenile delinquency is an intractable problem worldwide and has been increasing phenomenally by as much as 30 percent since the 1990s (World Youth Report, 2008). Antisocial behaviours of young people have been posing a lot of problems to the wellbeing of the people in Nigeria. Citizens, researchers and public officials perceive juvenile delinquency as a major social contemporary concern in Nigeria. Juvenile crimes witnessed in Nigeria include: drug abuse, cultism, bullying, truancy, examination malpractices, prostitution and theft (Ugwuoke, 2010).

Solomon (2014) defined delinquency as a relatively minor violation of legal or moral code by children or adolescents. However, no delinquent act should be considered as minor because any act of delinquency can result to serious damage. Juvenile delinquency is such behaviour by a young person (usually 16 or 18 years depending on the state code) that can bring him to the attention of a court. In a broadest sense according to Solomon (2014), a delinquent act is any behaviour of a young boy or girl that can be objected to by senior members of a society.

Forms of Juvenile Delinquency

Teens sometimes go completely off the hook and get themselves involved in petty crimes. If they are not discouraged or pulled out of the path, then they are likely to fall deeper into a life of crime. As a parent, it is your responsibility to keep an eye on your youngsters and do whatever it takes to keep them away from a life of crime. However, it's easier said than done because a lot of parents these days have absolutely no idea about juvenile crimes. That is why they are often unaware of the problem even when it is right in front of them. Realizing this lack of awareness, Secure Teen (2017) decided to outline the most common types of juvenile crimes that kids could get involved in.

1. Larceny

At a young age, kids are not capable of pulling off something big, but the smalltime crimes give them the thrill that they are seeking. They start with larceny and their criminal tendencies rise when they get away with it.

They steal from unsuspecting people and swipe things that are easily disposable or inexpensive. Not a lot of people report such incidents because the thing that gets stolen is not really worth a great deal of fuss. Since it does not get reported, no one goes looking for whoever committed the crime, so the child gets away with it. Now instead of thinking themselves as fortunate, kids become overconfident and start to think that they are capable of getting away with anything.

2. Assault

When youngsters become overconfident of their ability to get away with anything, they fearlessly assault defenceless people. They bully students at school and beat them up at every chance they get. Pushing or shoving people out of the way becomes almost a habit for them. Furthermore, they just can't stand someone disagreeing with them. They keep on arguing unless the other party gives in. If the other party stubbornly stands its ground, then they get a beat down.

3. Illegal Purchases

Smoking, drugs, and alcohol are considered cool among a lot of kids, especially those with delinquent tendencies. They go out of their way to get their hands on them and this can get them in a whole lot of trouble. First of all, they could go to prison if reported and caught. Secondly, they can get addicted to all of these substances. Just to deal with this addiction that they have brought upon themselves, they start to seek money, and to get it, they once again go back to larceny crimes. However, this time around, they don't limit their thefts to petty things. Instead, they begin aiming for things that can earn them a huge chunk of cash. They rob stores, steal cars, stick people up for cash, become drug distributors, etc.

It's tough to reform delinquent kids as once they have experienced everything, even jail, then they are not afraid to do anything. This is why parents must stay on their toes to prevent their youngsters from getting involved in such activities in the first place.

4. Truancy

National Policy on Education (2004) stated that the broad goal of the Secondary

School education is to prepare the students for "useful living within the society and to help them obtain higher education". To achieve this objective, the curriculum designed for secondary schools is made comprehensive and broad based, aimed at broadening students' knowledge and outlook, for this goal to be achieved in education truancy is one of the barriers which must be tackled.

5. Examination Malpractice:

Examination malpractices indulged in by secondary school students is another form of juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Kogi State. Students have designed diverse strategies for cheating, some of these tendencies may include; impersonation, taking in materials suspected to be relevant to the examination into examination hall, and copying from fellow examinees (Oguche, Yusuf, & Usman, 2023). Duze (2011) identified forms of cheating by students to include, sharing of, information among test takers, or the use of copied notes, script sheets, obtaining the questions or answers to a test ahead of time, and working on behalf of other students on essay, assignments or term papers.

Factors Responsible for Juvenile Delinquency among Students

With the rate of crimes being perpetrated by youths' day by day, there has been a lot of debate and concern on youth crime prevention. While there is a consensus on taking measures to save teens from going astray, very little seems to have been done in this regard. The primary reason for this is the misconception on the various factors responsible for these crimes which often ranges from armed robbery, kidnaping for ransom, raping, substance abuse and so on. The following are some of the factors responsible for juvenile delinquency and is supported by Wickliffe (2012):

a) Financial Hardship

Committing small crimes is one thing and becoming a full-fledged criminal is another. For a very long time, it was believed that it is the teenagers' brain that makes him a criminal, but the scientific studies have proved that it is not just the brain but also poverty that turns an innocent kid into a hardened criminal. It is natural for teens to compare themselves with others and when they feel that their friends are richer and financially more stable than them, they ultimately start looking for wrong ways to bridge the gap. Teens usually start off with small crimes like theft to fulfil their daily expenses, but with the passage of time, they keep falling deeper and deeper into the life of crime.

b) Peer Pressure

Peer pressure is yet another common reason behind an increase in the rate of juvenile delinquency. The surveys conducted on teen crimes have revealed that teens who are friends with criminals are more likely to end up becoming a criminal themselves. They generally spend most of their time with their friends, so it is quite natural for them to become influenced by the latter. Juvenile delinquency is mostly a team game. Teens prefer committing crimes in the form of groups as it becomes exciting and also decreases their chances of getting caught. This is why it is strongly recommended that you keep an eye on kid's friends.

c) Lack of Affection from Family

Teens need your love, affection and care more than anything else. Neglected teens are more prone to become criminals, as the lack of love and affection they feel they deserved from the family, and rightly so, make them angry and violent. They channelize their negative energy in committing crimes.

d) Bullying

Bullying is not just a crime itself, but it also gives birth to other crimes. Several studies have proved that teens who bully others have a tendency to become criminals in later stages of their lives. Abusive behaviour opens doors for crimes. Teens that show abusive behaviour or remain in a company of friends who exhibit abusive behaviour end up committing crimes. In some cases, the victims of bullying become criminal just to take revenge from the society.

e) Drug and Alcohol Abuse

There is a reason drugs and alcohol are prohibited for teens. Taking drugs or drinking alcohol as a minor is itself a crime, but it also leads to various other crimes. Drug and alcohol abuse affect the judgment of teens, increasing the probability of committing crimes like theft or vandalism. After getting drunk, their reasoning and judgment gets foggy, leading them to become part of a crime that they never intended to commit in the first place.

There is multitude of risk factors that exposes youths into juvenile infraction in the society. Delinquency is seen as extreme consequences of a child unsuccessful interaction with elements in his or her environment. According to the American Psychological Association cited in Nwachukwu (2018), juvenile delinquency is driven by negative consequences of social and economic development particularly economic crisis, political instability and the weakening of major institutions of society. Moreover, the transition for many children between family, school and work is increasingly challenged. The traditional pattern guiding the relationship and transition that will allow for smooth process of socialisation is presently collapsing with advent of modernisation and technological changes.

(f) Harmful Widowhood Practices

In Nigeria, like any other African Country, traditional practices like the issue of widowhood are still consciously and unconsciously upheld by significant proportion of the population. Widowhood is a tragedy that befalls a married person as a result of the timely or untimely death of the spouse, either the husband or the wife, thereby making the survival a widow or a widower a difficult one. Widowhood practices are observed by almost all the ethnic groups in Nigeria, particularly among the Yoruba, Igbo and Hausas. The culture of widowhood has been in existence from time immemorial and transmitted from generation to generation (Oguche, Afu & Osagie, 2024). This harmful widowhood practices tend to affect the upbringing of the child.

(g) Insecurity

Afu, Oguche, Usman and Gimba (2023) asserted that success in learning can only be achieved in the atmosphere of peace and tranquillity, and this can never be negotiated if educational goals and objectives must be achieved. Moreover, a restful academic environment is the determinant of academic success, and it is also the prerequisite of the progress and development of education.

Consequences of Juvenile Delinquency

Child delinquency, also known as juvenile offending, or youth crime, is participation in illegal behaviour by minors (juvenile) younger than the statutory age of maturity. Most legal systems prescribe specific procedures for dealing with juveniles, such as juvenile detention centres, and courts. A child delinquent is a person who is typically under the age of eighteen (18) and commits an act that otherwise would have been charged as a crime if they were adults. As a result of drug abuse, family members might fight a lot because of the problems the drug abuse is causing, the drug user might do and say things that upset neighbours and friends and make the family ashamed (Ifunanya & Emmanuel, 2022).

Factors contributing to delinquency are thus to be found not only in the mental and physical make-up of the individual, but also in his present and past environments. Unwholesome influences and difficult situations encountered in early childhood are probably as important causal factors of delinquency as are present conditions. They may even be more important. Therefore, parents and teachers should be very keen in monitoring children right from the very small age. A nation's future to a great extent depends on the human resource base of the nation. As part of the base is all citizens in the nation, so a nation that does not pay attention to the proper overall growth of its citizens stand a great chance to lose out in the development race. Nigeria, being a developing country has put some measures in place to ensure that children of school going age are in

school and are being offered the sort of education the nation requires for its development. What must be ensured is the proper implementation and supervision of programmes. In all, the adverse effects of juvenile, delinquency behaviour among the students manifest most when they drop out of school thereby constituting social nuisance as the male will take to armed robbery and the female prostitution, this therefore becomes a problem for the society.

Control Measures of Juvenile Delinquency among Secondary School Students

Naturally parents and teachers cannot be solely responsible for the prevention of child delinquency. The law enforcement agency, local and higher authority, electronic and printed media and other social organizations all have a role to play. Parents should monitor the kind of people or companion that their children walk with or the group they join in order to ascertain the purpose of the group whether good or bad so as to advise them accordingly. Again, the researcher also recommends that classrooms should not be crowded. Overcrowding makes discipline as well as good health among the pupil virtually impossible. Teachers are also able to monitor the activities of the students when the class is not crowded.

Counselling can also be used in assisting juvenile delinquent to give up the act. To this effect, when any form of juvenile delinquency behaviours are identified, school counsellors should ensure that they counsel the students so far identified. Parents should also try to provide some of the basic requirements their children need at school within their meagre resources. Due to the fact that truancy is a problem that not only affects the students, but also the students' family, school and the entire society, Michael et al (2005) in his article titled "Manual to Combat Truancy", suggested five primary elements of educational strategy to combat Juvenile delinquency act, they include:

1. Involve Parents in all Juvenile Delinquency Prevention Activities:

According to this element, parents play the fundamental role in the education of their children. Nobody else commands greater influence in getting young persons to go to school every day and recognising how a good education can define his future than the parents. For families and school to work together to solve problems like truancy there must be mutual trust and communication. Schools can also help by being "familyfriendly" and encouraging teachers and parents to make regular contact before problems arise. Schools should help in training of teachers to work with parents, hiring or appointing a parent liaison and to arrange for parent meetings through which parents will have a voice in school decisions; by so doing the problem of school truancy will be reduced.

2. Establish on-going Juvenile Delinquency Prevention Programmes in School:

Research findings has reviewed that juvenile delinquency is a symptom of a much larger problem. In order to curb this ugly incidence, schools should address underlying needs of each child to ensure that truancy is not a re-occurring behaviour. Also, students' basic educational needs such as conducive teaching and learning environment, adequate instructional materials and other academic facilities like library, laboratory and technical workshops and so on should be provided for students so as to help attract their regular school attendance (Michael et al, 2005).

3. Ensure that Students Face Firm Sanctions for Juvenile Delinquency behaviour:

For effective reduction of juvenile delinquency, schools must communicate to students and families that juvenile delinquency act will not be tolerated from any student and that any student found in this act must face severe and firm punishment from related school authorities.

4. Create Meaningful Incentives for Parental Responsibility:

This is also another suggested element on how juvenile delinquency can be curtailed among students. Following this principle, the school should create incentive programme both for the parents and children. Positive incentives such as participation in publicly funded activities and cash awards to be given to any parent who plays positive role in truancy reduction among students. On the other hand, negative sanctions like fines and imprisonment should be administered to parents who are naïve about their ward's irregular attendance to schools, all this will help to promote parental responsibility towards the reduction of truancy (Michael et al, 2005).

5. Involvement of Law Enforcement Agency in Juvenile Delinquency Reduction:

In order to enforce regular school attendance policies, school officials should establish close linkage with law enforcement agents like police, Nigeria Security and Civil Defence Corps (NSCDC), female squad officer, Juvenile and family court officials sop on to help prosecute any student caught in any act of juvenile delinquent behaviour (Michael et al, 2005). To crown it all, government should help the police department and court system to establish and run temporary detention centres where they can drop-off school truants. Also, the government should as well embark on some other anti- truancy initiatives like Operation Sweep Students Truants in neighbourhoods. With these suggestions, truancy among secondary school students and even those in primary and tertiary institution will be reduced if not eradicated.

Theoretical Framework

For the purpose of this study, two theories will be adopted. These theories include operant conditioning theory and Strain theory. These theories, aim to ascertain reasons behind what makes people engage in certain act. These theories shall be discussed distinctly as presented below.

1. Operant Conditioning Theory

American psychologist Skinner (1938) propounded the theory of operant conditioning in the United State of America. Skinner conducted research on shaping behaviour through positive and negative reinforcement and demonstrated operant conditioning, a behaviour modification technique which he developed in contrast with classical conditioning. His idea of the behaviour modification technique was to put the subject on a program with steps. The steps would be setting goals which would help you determine how the subject would be changed by following the steps. The program design is designing a program that will help the subject to reach the desired state. Then implementation and evaluation which is putting the programme to use and then evaluating the effectiveness of it.

The above theory of operant conditioning propounded by B.F. Skinner can be used to curb the menace of examination malpractices, this can be done by making sure that, students who don't get involved in examination malpractices should be rewarded in order to sustain such behaviour why those students who are found guilty of

examination malpractices should be allowed to face stiff punishment in order to discourage such behaviour in our society.

2. Strain Theory

This theory was first proposed by Robert Merton in 1938. Emile Durkheim, a French Sociologist had first employed the concept of anomie to describe the social malaise that accompanied the breakdown of existing social rules and values brought about by rapid social change. When established norms, customs and practices are made obsolete the result is a collective sense of social insecurity and normlessness. Anomic conditions arise when the rule of law becomes weakened and powerless to maintain social control. Under this condition, crime can be considered a 'normal' response to existing social conditions. When juveniles experience strain or stress, they become upset and they sometimes engage in delinquency as a result. They may engage in delinquency to reduce or escape from the strain they are experiencing. For example, a student may engage in violence so as to end harassment from others. A former student may become aggressive so as to stop others from bullying him/her. One may steal to reduce financial problems. Another one may turn to deviant peers to escape from harassment by the bigger students. Students may also perform delinquent acts to seek revenge against those who have wronged them. They may engage in illicit drug use in an effort to feel better.

Many of the delinquent acts can be expressed using this strain theory. Most of the delinquent acts are committed as a result of a strain or stress. All strain theorists argue that a major type of strain is that failure to achieve one's goals. They argue that many adolescents place special emphasis on certain goals and that the failure to achieve these goals contributes to higher levels of delinquency. These goals include money, status or respect and autonomy from parents and teachers. Adolescents in school need money for 'bread, sugar, butter, nice shoes, uniform etc. however, most from the poor backgrounds are not able to obtain the money they need through legal channels such as parents and work. As a consequence, such adolescents experience a strain and they may attempt to get the money through illegal channels such as stealing items like calculators, textbooks etc., prostitution and selling drugs. Closely related to the desire for money is the desire for status and respect. People want to be positively regarded by others and they want to be treated respectfully, which at a minimum involves being treated in a fair or just manner.

Most male juveniles experience difficulties in their desire to be treated as men. Such juveniles may attempt to 'accomplish masculinity' through delinquency. They may engage in delinquent acts to demonstrate that they possess traits like toughness, dominance and independence. They may fight to force others into giving them the respect they believe they deserve as 'real men'. This may explain why we have bullies in schools. These juveniles may also adopt a tough demeanor, respond to even minor shows of disrespect with violence and occasionally assault or rob others in an effort to establish a tough reputation. One study that has examined the relationship between autonomy and delinquency found out that adolescents with a strong need for autonomy were higher in delinquency and that one of the reasons for their behavior was that they were angrier and more frustrated. These are some of those who will fight with teachers because they do not want to do their homework or clean up their classes or dormitories (Sambo, 2008). Others engage in delinquent acts like cheating in exams because they are unable to achieve the academic grades that are expected of them.

The above theory explained in details factors necessitating juvenile delinquency which is the topic of discussion. The theory which is the foundation of this present study is the theory of B. F. Skinner which focuses on reinforcing good behaviour and withholding reinforcement for undesirable behaviour which is also term as punishment. The theory can be used to solve the problem of juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Kogi State by reinforcing the students who does not get involved in any forms of juvenile delinquency acts and sanctions those students who get involved.

Research Design

The design adopted for this study is descriptive survey research design. This is a research method that describes a given state of affairs at a particular time (Olayiwola; Afu, Oguche, Usman and Gimba, 2023). This research design permits the gathering of information through the use of questionnaire from a population based on appropriate sampling techniques. Also, descriptive survey research was considered suitable since it would solicit for information or responses from the respondents on the problem under investigation. It was on this basis that the researcher decided to use descriptive survey design.

Population of the Study

The population of this study comprises of SS 1 students attending Public Senior Secondary Schools in Kogi State. The total number of Public senior secondary schools in Kogi State are 163 and the total number of students in all the public senior secondary schools in Kogi State is 39,542 (Educational Zonal Office, Statistical Department, Kogi State, 2019). While the total number of SS1 students in the six selected secondary schools stands at 2,573.

Sample Size and Sampling Procedure

The sample size for this study is 254 taking from the total number of 2, 573 students in six public senior secondary schools in Kogi State. The selection of the sample size was based on the recommendations of Krejci and Morgan (1976) Table for demining sample sizes of a specific population.

Instrumentation

The instrument used in data collection for this study was a self-structured Students Instrument on Juvenile Delinquency Questionnaire (SIJDQ) constructed by the researcher. The instrument consisted of two sections A and B. Section A 'comprised bio- data of the respondents while section B 'consisted of 42 items on the Factors, Consequences and Control of Juvenile Delinquency among Secondary School Students. The instrument was designed along the four-point scale format of Strongly Agree (SA - 4), Agree (A - 3), Disagree (D - 2), Strongly Disagree (SD - 1) where the respondents indicated their options on the items of the instrument

Validity and Reliability of the Instrument

To ensure the validity of the instrument. The questionnaire was subjected to face, content and construct validity by the researcher's supervisors to ensure that the items of the questionnaire adequately covered the research questions for the study and also to ensure language appropriateness. This was done and approved before the field survey.

To ensure the reliability of the instrument, a pilot test was carried out using 20 students in Government secondary school Ankpa, Kogi State who were not part of the main sample for study. The reliability of the

instrument was calculated using test-retest. Pearson product moment co-efficient of correlation was adopted to determine the reliability of the instrument. The result of the pilot test produced an index of 0.78 which was adequate to make the instrument reliable for the study.

Data Collection Procedure

The copies of the questionnaire were taken to the various schools and administered to students by the researcher, with the help of two research assistants. The researcher and the research assistants explained the relevance of the study to the respondents and to ensure they give their maximum cooperation by providing responses to the questionnaire. All the responses were collected by the researcher and tabulated ready for statistical analysis.

Method of Data Analysis

The data collected was subjected to statistical analysis, interpretation and discussion. Simple percentages, frequency count and mean score were used for demographic data and the research questions. The research questions were graded on a score of 2.50. Any item with a mean score of 2.50 and above was considered as “Agree” while those scores below the mean score of 2.50 were considered “Disagree”. All the hypotheses of this study were tested using t-test. t-test was considered suitable for testing all the hypotheses because it is a statistical tool that allows for the determination of the differences between the means of two variables. All the hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance.

Data Presentation

The data presented and analysed in this chapter deals with the demographic data, answering of research questions, testing of hypotheses and summary of findings. The data presented is based on a sample size of 254.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by Gender

Gender	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male	161	63.4
Female	93	36.6
Total	254	100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2021

In the above demographic data of the respondent's gender, it shows that 161 representing (63.4 %) are males while 93 representing (36.6 %) are females. This implies that the number of male respondents exceeded that of the female respondents.

Table 2: Distribution of Respondents by their Location

Location	Frequency	Percent
Urban	90	35.4
Rural	164	64.6

Total 254 100.0

Source: Field Survey, 2021

Table 3 shows that out of the total number of 254 respondents, 90 representing (35.4%) were from the urban schools. The remaining 164 representing (64.6%) are from the rural schools. This implies that the number of students from rural schools exceeded that of the urban schools.

Answers to Research Questions

This section contains data of the research questions raised to guide this study.

Research Question One: What are the Factors Responsible for Juvenile Delinquency among Secondary School Students in Kogi State?

Table 4: Various Factors Responsible Juvenile Delinquency among Secondary School Students in Kogi State

State-Statements N=254				Mea n	SD	Decision
1. Parental attitudes toward their children are one of the factors causing juvenile delinquency among students	4			2.96	0.6	Agreed
2. Inadequate supervision arising from family structure causes juvenile delinquency among students	7			3.35	0.8	Agreed
3. Peer group influence	7	3.45	0.6			Agreed
4. Environmental factors	3		2.56	0.8		Agreed
5. Poverty and unemployment are also one of the major causes of juvenile delinquency among students	1			3.26	0.8	Agreed
6. Physical factors such as speech defects and deformity cause juvenile delinquencies among students	9			2.41	0.7	Disagree
7. Lack of cordial relationship between students and teachers causes juvenile delinquencies	1			2.69	0.8	Agreed
8. Inadequate school building and equipment causes juvenile delinquencies among students	4			2.60	0.7	Agreed
9. Congested neighbourhood and slums cause juvenile delinquency	0			3.23	0.7	Agreed
10. Social media or technological advancement leads to juvenile delinquency	2			2.51	0.7	Agreed
11. Incompetence and unprofessional teachers contributed to juvenile delinquency among students	5			2.89	0.8	Agreed
12. Poor parent-children communication led children to find solace other than homes	1			3.15	0.8	Agreed

13.	Lack of social and moral training	3.14	0.7	Agreed
7				
14.	Poor classroom management	2.47	0.8	Disagreed
15.	Drugs and alcohol abuse	3.20	0.6	Agreed
9	Overall Mean	2.92	0.3	Agreed

Table 4 above with the overall mean score of 2.92 presents the various factors of Juvenile Delinquency among secondary school students in Kogi State. From the analysis, it was discovered that over average of the respondents agreed all the items in table 3 as the major factors of juvenile delinquencies among Secondary School Students in Kogi State, Nigeria except item 6 and 14 which has mean scores of 2.41 and 2.47 that were less than the criterion value of 2.50.

Research Question Two: What are the Consequences of Juvenile Delinquency among Secondary School Students in Kogi State?

f respondents on the Consequences of Juvenile Delinquency among Secondary School Students in Kogi State, Nigeria: N=254

Table 5: Frequency and mean scores o

S/N	Statement	Mean	St. dev.	Decision
16.	Juvenile delinquency has constituted a problem that has led to students' attrition	3.28	0.72	Agreed
17.	Destruction of school property	3.24	0.76	Agreed
18.	Poor students' academic performance	3.21	0.78	Agreed
19.	<u>Truancy and lateness of student to school</u>	<u>3.23</u>	<u>0.74</u>	<u>Agreed</u>
20.	Rudeness and sexual harassment	2.89	0.71	Agreed
21.	Raping of fellow students	3.07	0.69	Agreed
22.	Fighting and killing of fellow students	2.99	0.84	Agreed
23.	Juvenile delinquency contributes to students' involvement in armed robbery	3.26	0.71	Agreed
24.	Students becoming a drug addict	3.29	0.77	Agreed
25.	Juvenile delinquency constitutes serious impediment to development	3.06	0.69	Agreed
26.	Lack of respect for elders	3.34	0.67	Agreed
27.	Lack of respect for constituted authority	3.16	0.79	Agreed
Overall Mean		3.17	0.13	Agreed

Items in table 5 above which has overall mean score of 3.17 elicited responses on the consequences of juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Kogi State. From the analysis, it was discovered that over average of the respondents agreed to all the items in Table 5 as the major consequences of juvenile delinquency among Secondary School Students in Kogi State which is in line with the decision rule that 2.50 and above be agreed and below be disagreed.

Research Question Three: What are the Control Measures of Juvenile Delinquency among Secondary School Students in Kogi State?

Table 6: Frequency and mean scores of respondents on the Control Measures of Juvenile Delinquency among Secondary School Students in Kogi State, Nigeria:

N=254

S/N	Statement	Mean	St. Dev.	Decision
28.	Provision of professional teachers	3.20	0.79	Agreed
29.	Adoption of proper teaching methodology	3.11	0.76	Agreed
30.	Creation of conducive learning environment	3.43	0.72	Agreed
31.	Provision of teaching materials	3.00	0.79	Agreed
32.	Paying of teachers' salary as at when due	3.07	0.74	Agreed
33.	Cordial relationship between the teachers and the students	3.22	0.73	Agreed
34.	Cordial relationship between the parents and their children	3.16	0.74	Agreed
35.	Effective communication between the parents and their children	3.20	0.86	Agreed
36.	Provision of professional counsellors in school	3.21	0.86	Agreed
37.	Creation of juvenile courts	3.19	0.82	Agreed
38.	Parents should monitor the kind of people their children associate with	3.12	0.67	Agreed
39.	Children should not be giving too much idle time	2.57	0.98	Agreed
40.	Necessary sanction should be applied without favour on any students who commit any forms of juvenile delinquency	3.14	0.80	Agreed
41.	Teachers should be good role model to their students	3.04	0.78	Agreed
42.	Involvement of law enforcement agency in juvenile delinquency reduction	2.96	0.91	Agreed
Overall Mean		3.11	0.19	Agreed

Table 6 above which have overall mean score of 3.11 presented the control measures of juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Kogi State. From the analysis, it was discovered that over average of the respondents agreed that all the above items mentioned in table 6 are some of the control measures of juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Kogi State which is in line with the decision rule that 2.50 and above be agreed and below be disagreed.

Testing of Hypotheses

The null hypotheses were tested using t-test statistics. All tests were conducted at $P > 0.05$ level of significance.

H₀₁: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of male and female students regarding the consequences of juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Kogi State.

Table 7: t-test results on the mean ratings of male and female students regarding the consequences of juvenile delinquency

Variables	N	X	SD	Df	t-value	Sig.(P)	Decision
Male	161	2.61	1.50	252	9.833	<0.001	Rejected
Female	93	2.56	1.69				

***=significant at 0.05 level ($p < 0.05$)**

The analysis on table 7 was carried out to determine whether there is any significant difference in the mean rating of male and female students on the consequences of juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Kogi State. A significant value of <0.001 (less than the 0.05 level of significance) was recorded. This shows that there was a significant difference. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis. This implies that there is a significant difference between male and female students as regards to the consequences of juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Kogi State.

H₀₂: There is no significant difference in the mean ratings of rural and urban students regarding the consequences of juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Kogi State.

Table 8: t-test results on the mean ratings of rural and urban students regarding the consequences of juvenile delinquency

Variables	N	X	SD	Df	t-value	Sig.(P)	Decision
Urban	90	2.61	1.08	252	4.754	.002	Rejected
Rural	164	2.56	1.10				

***=significant at 0.05 level ($p < 0.05$)**

The analysis on table 8 was carried out to determine whether there is any significant difference in the mean ratings of students in rural and urban schools regarding the consequences of juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Kogi State. A significant value of .002 (less than the 0.05 level of significance) was recorded. This shows that there was a significant difference. The null hypothesis was therefore rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis. This implies that there is a significant difference in the mean ratings of students in rural and urban schools regarding the consequences of juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Kogi State.

Findings

The study revealed the followings:

1. The findings of the study revealed that, parental attitudes toward their children such as inadequate supervision arising from family structure, peer group influence, environmental factors, poverty and unemployment, lack of cordial relationship between students and teachers, inadequate school building and equipment, congested neighbourhood and slums, social media or technological advancement, incompetence and unprofessional teachers, poor parent-children communication leading children to find solace other than homes,

lack of social and moral training and drugs and alcohol abuse are some of the major factors of juvenile delinquency among Secondary School Students in Kogi State, Nigeria.

2. Students' attrition, destruction of school property, poor students' academic performance, truancy and lateness of student to school, rudeness and sexual harassment, raping of fellow students, fighting and killing of fellow students, armed robbery, drug addict, serious impediment to development, lack of respect for elders and lack of respect for constituted authority are some of the major consequences of juvenile delinquency among Secondary School Students in Kogi State, Nigeria

3. Provision of professional teachers, adoption of proper teaching methodology, creation of conducive learning environment, provision of teaching materials, paying of teachers salary, cordial relationship between the teachers and the students, cordial relationship between the parents and their children, effective communication between the parents and their children, provision of professional counsellors in school, creation of juvenile courts, parents should monitor the kind of people their children associate with, children should not be giving too much idle time, necessary sanction should be applied without favour on any students who commit any forms of juvenile delinquency, teachers should be good role model to their students and involvement of law enforcement agency in juvenile delinquency reduction are the major control of juvenile delinquency among secondary school students in Kogi State.

4. The findings of the study also revealed that, there is a significant difference between male and female students as regards to the consequences of juvenile delinquencies among secondary school students in Kogi State. The difference is that, male students are more aware of the consequences of juvenile delinquency among students than their female students.

5. The findings of the study revealed that, there is a significant difference in the mean ratings of students in rural and urban schools regarding the consequences of juvenile delinquencies among secondary school students in Kogi State. The difference is that, students from urban areas are more aware of the consequences of juvenile delinquency among students than students' rural areas.

Conclusion

Based on the above findings of the study, juvenile delinquency has negative consequences on students' academic performance; the respondents confirmed the evils of juvenile delinquency and their long-term effects which include the production of corrupt and immoral citizens. Thus, if juvenile delinquency goes unchecked, our society would be stooped in endless immorality thus, efforts to curb juvenile delinquency among secondary school students should be supported by every well-meaning Nigerians. Therefore, we need to see to it that normalcy is restored to our education system by adhering to sustainable measures which would help all nations to move forward toward achieving zero tolerance on the issues of Juvenile delinquency.

Recommendations

Based on the findings and the conclusion of this study, the following recommendations are made;

1. The factors responsible for juvenile delinquencies in secondary schools can be eradicated or controlled if school administrators could ensure that they do all they can to prevent or reduce the level of juvenile

delinquency among secondary school students in order to avert the negative consequences it has on students' general well-being.

2. In order to avert the consequence of juvenile delinquency has on students, the study recommended that, the teachers and parents should encourage students to cultivate good/positive study attitude to help reduce act of juvenile delinquency in secondary schools.

3. The possible ways of controlling juvenile delinquency among students as recommended by the study is that, students that do not get involved in juvenile delinquency acts should be commended while those caught misbehaving should be given appropriate punishment to serve as deterrence to others.

4. The study recommends that parents, teachers and counsellor should intensify efforts towards helping the students who are at the receiving ends overcome the consequences of juvenile delinquencies the effort should focused more on female students who are revealed by the study to be less aware of the consequences of juvenile delinquency.

5. The study further recommends that all the stakeholders in education should make more efforts towards helping the students in rural to overcome the consequences of juvenile delinquencies by creating more awareness on the consequences of juvenile delinquency.

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